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THE ESSENCE OF THE CONCEPTS “DISCOURSE” AND “PUBLICISTIC DISCOURSE”

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Annotation. *This article explores the complex concepts of “discourse” and “publicistic discourse”. Discourse, lacking a single definition, refers to contextualized language use studied across disciplines. Publicistic discourse illuminates social life through diverse oral and written genres. It influences public opinion, reflects social mentalities, and guides societal development. The publicistic style takes written forms like articles and essays, and oral forms like speeches and commentaries, each with unique linguistic features shaped by communicative purposes.*

Keywords: *discourse, publicistic discourse, discourse analysis, language and society, communication, mass media, public opinion, social influence, linguistic genres, functional linguistics, sociolinguistics.*

Introduction

The process of globalization is stimulating the expansion of communication fields worldwide and the rapid development of new types of discourses and discourse studies. Defining the exact meaning and linguistic status of the concept “discourse” remains a complex issue to this day. As Y. Kubryakova noted, there is no single definition in linguistics that can fully reveal the essence of discourse.

The concept of discourse is widely used not only in linguistics but also in various fields of social sciences and can be interpreted differently in various contexts. The term “discourse” is actively used in fields such as linguistics, anthropology, literary studies, ethnography, sociology, sociolinguistics, philosophy, psycholinguistics, and cognitive psychology. This demonstrates the multifaceted and complex nature of discourse analysis. It is difficult to establish precise and rigid definitions in discourse analysis because it is always formed and developed within the framework of constantly changing social and cultural contexts.

Discourse analysis studies the use of language and speech in various spheres of social life. It analyzes speech and written texts in their social, political, cultural, and historical contexts. Through discourse analysis, issues such as social relations, power structures, and the formation of identities are also examined.

In the modern world, new types of discourses are emerging due to the rapid development of globalization and information technologies. In particular, online communications on the internet and social networks, as well as interactions in virtual worlds, are giving rise to distinctive types of discourse. These new discourses are being actively studied by linguists, sociolinguists, and specialists from other fields.

Literature review

In European linguistics, the concepts of discourse and publicistic discourse have been deeply studied by scholars such as T. van Dijk, N. Fairclough, and R. Wodak. For instance, van Dijk interpreted discourse as a socio-cognitive phenomenon, thoroughly analyzing its structure and production process. Fairclough studied discourse as a social practice, paying particular attention to its ideological and power-related aspects. Wodak investigated publicistic discourse based on critical discourse analysis methods, using it to deeply analyze social issues.

In American linguistics, discourse and publicistic discourse have been studied from the perspectives of pragmatics, sociolinguistics, and communicative linguistics. Specifically, D. Schiffrin interpreted discourse as a pragmatic phenomenon, analyzing its structure and functions. R. Lakoff studied publicistic discourse from the viewpoint of communicative linguistics, analyzing the communicative strategies used in it.

In Russian linguistics, discourse and publicistic discourse have been researched within the framework of traditional Russian linguistics, communicative linguistics, and pragmatics. For example, N. Arutyunova studied discourse from the perspective of traditional Russian linguistics, analyzing its semantic and pragmatic features. V. Karasik examined publicistic discourse from a communicative-pragmatic angle, revealing its distinctive characteristics.

Research methodology

This research on “discourse” and “publicistic discourse” primarily employs a qualitative methodology based on an extensive literature review and conceptual analysis. The study synthesizes perspectives from European, American, and Russian linguistics, incorporating historical-etymological analysis, genre classification, and functional examination of publicistic discourse in various societal contexts.

Discussion and results:

The concept of discourse was initially introduced into linguistics by French linguist E. Benveniste, who gave a new terminological meaning to the French word “discours”. According to etymological analyses, the word “discourse” comes from the

French “discours”, which in turn derives from the Latin “discursus”. “Discursus” initially meant “running”, and later “conversation”. In Medieval Latin, it expressed the meaning of “reasoning”. The word “discursus” was formed from the verb “discurrere”, which in Latin meant “to run, to run hurriedly”, and later “to examine a topic, to speak in detail about a subject, to reason”. Thus, the term “discourse” began to be used mainly to denote the process of oral and written communication.

V. Zvegintsev’s definition of discourse as “a linguistic area hidden behind clouds” does not, in our opinion, mean that it is impossible to fully reveal its essence. Although traditional linguistic approaches to studying discourse have certain limitations, it would be incorrect to completely reject them.

Moreover, discourse is also defined as “a text integrated with non-linguistic factors (pragmatic, socio-cultural, psychological); a text viewed from the perspective of events occurring; speech interpreted as purposeful social action”. In this definition, we can see that the concepts of “text” and “speech activity” are used equally in identifying the phenomenon of discourse.

N. Arutyunova’s definition of discourse shows its connection with text and speech activity. However, this definition also interprets the concept of discourse somewhat narrowly. This is because discourse is closely linked not only to text and speech but also to the context in which they occur and the relationships between participants.

Y. Stepanov studies discourse as a phenomenon reflecting the interconnection between language and socio-cultural factors. In his view, discourse is an important means of expressing the unique mentality of a particular society or group. The scholar defines discourse as a “mental world created by adhering to special grammatical and lexical rules”. According to his approach, each social group or community has its own unique discourse that reflects their worldview, values, and beliefs.

The concept of “publicistic discourse” is a product of oral and written creativity that illuminates social life. The origin of this term is related to the Latin word “publicus” (public) and the English word “publicist” (a journalist writing about politics and state affairs). Publicism is recognized as a distinct artistic genre that deals with reflecting, evaluating, and generalizing current issues in society.

Publicistic discourse manifests in both oral and written forms. Oral publicism includes speeches, radio and television appearances, while written publicism encompasses newspaper and magazine articles, essays, and other similar genres. Modern publicism is also widely spread in the form of internet blogs and social media posts. However, it’s difficult to strictly delineate the genres of publicistic discourse because publicistic works often blend with literary-artistic, popular scientific, and official-bureaucratic styles. They combine facts with artistic color and imagery.

When discussing the main characteristics and functions of publicistic discourse, it's important to emphasize its role and significance in society. Publicism plays a crucial role in the socio-political life of society. It attracts public attention by covering topical issues and analyzing important problems. In this way, publicism serves to shape public opinion and guide society's development in a certain direction.

Among the distinctive aspects of publicistic discourse, its ability to communicate with a wide audience should be particularly noted. In their works, publicists engage in direct dialogue with representatives of various social strata. This further expands the sphere of influence of publicism.

Moreover, publicism is important in influencing readers and shaping their worldview and way of thinking. Publicistic works not only increase the intellectual level of their readers but also cultivate moral and ethical qualities in them.

The publicistic style, according to its functional purpose, has similarities with various forms of public speech, including political speech, radio language, and film and television speech. Together with these speech forms, the publicistic style constitutes a broader unit generally referred to as mass media styles. Mass media profoundly influence the consciousness, lifestyle, culture, and language of the entire society. As a functional style of speech, the publicistic style encompasses various genres such as articles, essays, reportages, feuilletons, and interviews.

I. Galperin divides the publicistic style into written and oral forms, analyzing their distinctive features and functions.

According to him, the written publicistic style encompasses the following genres:

1. Essay language. In essays, the author strives to express their thoughts clearly and consistently. Such works rely on both subjective reflections and objective facts. The linguistic features of essays share similarities with scientific, educational, and artistic styles.

2. Newspaper articles. Articles in daily or weekly publications inform readers about current events and issues. The language of newspaper articles reflects the changing socio-political situation and employs linguistic means characteristic of artistic, official-bureaucratic, and colloquial styles.

3. Journal articles. Journal articles on literary-critical and socio-political topics provide comprehensive analysis of complex issues and stimulate discussion. Their language consists of a blend of scientific and publicistic styles.

4. Treatises. Treatises are strictly structured texts of scientific or intellectual orientation, providing detailed information on a specific topic. The language of treatises is close to the scientific style.

Oral publicistic discourse includes the following:

1. Public speech style. This style is used by speakers at political gatherings, conferences, and public events to attract listeners to their ideas, persuade them, and encourage action. Such speeches are dominated by expressive, impactful, and emotional linguistic means.

2. Radio commentary language. News, sports, and cultural event commentaries broadcast via radio provide quick and lively information. Commentators try to capture listeners' attention by conveying events accurately and interestingly. The language of radio commentaries also places great emphasis on expressiveness and emotionality.

According to I.R. Galperin's classification, the publicistic style has both written and oral forms, each with its own linguistic characteristics. At the same time, the linguistic means in these forms are selected and applied in accordance with their functional purposes.

Conclusion.

We've seen that discourse and publicistic discourse are complex ideas that mean different things to different people. Publicistic discourse, whether in writing or speech, plays a big role in shaping what people think and how society develops. It's a powerful way to talk about important issues and reach many people. As our world changes with new technology, new types of discourse are appearing. This means there's still a lot to learn about how language is used in society. While we've covered a lot, there's always more to discover about how we communicate and influence each other through various forms of discourse.

REFERENCES

1. Арутюнова Н.Д. Дискурс // Лингвистический энциклопедический словарь. – 1990. – С. 136-137.
2. Долгушина Е.К. Особенности языка современной массовой и качественной прессы России (Лексический аспект): дисс. ... канд. фило
3. Карасик В.И. О типах дискурса // Языковая личность: институциональный и персональный дискурс. – 2000. – С. 5-20.
4. Кубрякова Й.С. О понятиях дискурса и дискурсивного анализа в современной лингвистике // Дискурс, речь, речевая деятельность: функциональные и структурные аспекты. – 2000. – С. 7-25.
5. Мисуно Е.А., Шаблыгина И.В. Перевод с английского на русский язык: практикум: учеб. пособие. – Минск: Аверсэв, 2009. – 255 с.
6. Online Etymology Dictionary. Discourse. – URL: <https://www.etymonline.com/word/discourse>

7. Степанов Ю.С. Альтернативный мир, Дискурс, Факт и принцип Причинности // Язык и наука конца XX века. – 1995. – С. 35-73.
8. Fairclough N. Media Discourse. – London: Edward Arnold, 1995. – 214 p.
9. Lakoff R.T. Talking Power: The Politics of Language in Our Lives. – New York: Basic Books, 1990. – 324 p.
10. Schiffrin D. Approaches to Discourse. – Oxford: Blackwell, 1994. – 470 p.
11. Thurlow C., Mroczek K. (Eds.). Digital discourse: Language in the new media. – Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2011. – 364 p.
12. Van Dijk T.A. Discourse and context: A sociocognitive approach. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2008. – 283 p.
13. Van Dijk T.A. News as Discourse. – Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, 1988. – 200 p.
14. Wodak R. What CDA is about - a summary of its history, important concepts and its developments // Methods of Critical Discourse Analysis / Ed. by R. Wodak, M. Meyer. – London: SAGE Publications, 2001. – P. 1-13.